

NONLINEAR VISCOELASTICITY OF HIGH MODULUS FIBERS

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Fiberglass, Kevlar and Graphite fibers have moduli ranging from 50 to 200 GPa; and breaking stress ranging from 2.5 to 3.3 GPa at 1.4 to 4.2% breaking elongation. These high modulus fibers are candidate materials for many fiber reinforced composites. Experimental evidence showed that these fibers have nonlinear stress-strain relationships which depend on strain history. The stress-strain relationships of these fibers were represented by a cubic spline function. Based on the stress relaxation behavior observed under initial loads ranging from 5 to 80% of the breaking load of the fibers, one dimensional constitutive equations were developed for these fibers using a quasilinear viscoelastic model in terms of a continuous relaxation spectrum. When sufficient information on the creep and dynamic mechanical behavior of these fibers is available, the quasilinear viscoelastic model should provide a unified representation of the material properties of the high modulus fibers.

INTRODUCTION

Prudent design of fiber reinforced composite structures requires careful analysis of the stress-strain-time behavior of fibers and fiber assemblies in the composite structure. Necessary for such analysis is the knowledge of the viscoelastic behavior of fibers over a wide range of stress-strain-time domain, stress and strain programs and varied environment as possible.

In order to generate design data for fabric reinforced composites, the viscoelastic behavior of fiberglass, Kevlar 49 and graphite single filaments were characterized. Based on experimental observations, one dimensional constitutive equations were established for these fibers using a quasilinear viscoelastic model in terms of a continuous relaxation spectrum.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and Specimen Preparation

Fiberglass ECG37, Kevlar 49 and Thornel 300 graphite yarns were obtained from the Owens-Corning Fiberglas Inc., duPont and Union Carbide, respectively. Table 1 gives a summary of the details on the yarns.

Table 1. Material Information			
Fiber	Yarn Linear Density, Tex	Fiber Linear Density, Tex	Fiber Specific Gravity, g/cc
Fiberglass ECG37 1/0	134	.163	2.54
Graphite, Thornel 300 Grade WYP 15 1/0	396	.067	1.73
Kevlar 49	111	.158	1.45

Tex = mg/meter

Individual fibers were removed carefully from the yarn bundles and each fiber was mounted with an epoxy resin on a paper frame which had an opening equivalent to the testing gauge length of 1.3 cm.

Tensile Testing

Simple elongation experiments were done at a strain rate of $.017 \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Cyclic loading experiments were carried out at $6.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, $3.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $3.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Stress relaxation behavior of the fibers was observed for 1000 seconds under initial loads ranging from 5 to 80% of the breaking load.

All the tensile tests were carried out on an Instron tensile tester at 65% RH and 21°C. A desk top computer was used for data acquisition and processing.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Experimental Results

Fig. 1 shows the stress-strain curves of the fibers. The breaking stress, elongation and the apparent (or secant) modulus of the fiber are summarized in Table 2.

Fiber	No. of Observations	Breaking Stress GPa	Breaking Elongation %	Apparent Modulus GPa
E-Glass	12	2.56 ± .49	4.2 ± .8	61
Kevlar 49	9	3.28 ± .6	3.5 ± .6	94
Graphite	13	2.6 ± .62	1.4 ± .3	186

1 GPa ~ 10 g/den ~ 128 ksi

Close inspection of the stress-strain curves indicated that the slopes of the stress-strain curves were not constant. This is demonstrated in Fig. 2 to Fig. 4. A cubic spline interpolation technique was used to obtain a quantitative representation of the stress-strain behavior. The slopes of the stress-strain curves were conveniently computed by taking the derivatives of the stress-strain functions with respect to the strain. A plot of the slopes of the stress-strain curve as a function of strain in Fig. 2 shows that the slopes (or moduli) of fiberglass vary from 56 to 66 GPa. In Fig. 3, we can see the moduli of Kevlar fibers vary from ~80 to 100 GPa. The moduli of graphite fibers vary from 170 to 200 GPa, as shown in Fig. 4. A plot of the slopes of the stress-strain curve as a function of strain shows a magnified view of the change of the stress-strain response as the fiber is being deformed. Figs. 3 and 4 show that Kevlar and graphite fibers tend to strain harden.

Figure 1. Stress-Strain Curves of High Modulus Fibers

Figure 2. Stress-Strain Curve (o) and Slopes of the Stress-Strain Curve (.) of Fiberglass Filaments

Figure 3. Stress-Strain Curve (o) and Slopes (.) of the Stress-Strain Curve of Kevlar Filaments

Figure 4. Stress-Strain Curve (o) and Slopes of the Stress-Strain Curve (.) of Graphite Filaments

Measurement of hysteresis loss reflects the mechanical reversibility and the viscous response of fibers. The hysteresis loss of the high modulus fibers is quite insensitive to strain rate. For example, as shown in Fig. 5, a ten-fold increase in strain rate causes little increase in hysteresis loss for Kevlar fiber.

Figure 5. Hysteresis Loops of Kevlar Fibers at Various Strain Rates Under Cyclic Loading

The stress relaxation behavior of the high modulus fibers are shown in Figs. 6, 7 and 8, plotting load as a function of time in logarithmic scale. The rate of stress relaxation tends to increase as the level of initial load (or strain level) increases. Even though the apparent modulus of fiberglass is lower than Kevlar and graphite fibers, it appears that fiberglass is more stable under long term loading.

Figure 6. Stress-Relaxation of Fiberglass Filaments at Various Maximum Loads

Figure 7. Stress Relaxation of Kevlar Filaments at Various Maximum Loads

Figure 8. Stress Relaxation of Graphite Filaments at Various Max. Loads

Analysis

Experimental evidence showed that the high modulus fibers have nonlinear stress-strain behavior which depend on strain history. Hysteresis losses were not proportional to strain rate. These are characteristics of nonlinear viscoelastic materials. A quasilinear viscoelastic model was used to represent the experimental observations. The basis and the computational aspects of the quasilinear viscoelastic model has been detailed by Ko [1,2], consequently, only a brief outline of the model is presented herein. The stress response $K(\lambda, t)$ for an instantly applied strain history $\lambda(t) = 1 + (\lambda - 1)H(t)$ is a function of the extension ratio λ and time t . Our experimental results suggest that $K(\lambda, t)$ may be written in the form:

$$K(\lambda, t) = T^e(\lambda)G(t) \quad (1)$$

Then, a one dimensional constitutive equation can be written in the following form:

$$T(t) = T^e[\lambda(t)] + \int_0^t T^e[\lambda(t)] \dot{G}(t-\tau) d\tau \quad (2)$$

The first term on the left-hand side of Eq. (2) accounts for the elastic response which is reflected in the stress-strain curve. The elastic response can be quantified by a cubic spline function (1,3):

$$T_1^e(\lambda) = \sum_{j=0}^3 B_{ij} \lambda^j \quad (3)$$

$$i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$$

$$B_{00} = 0$$

$$B_{ij} = \text{material coefficients}$$

The second term in Eq. (2) accounts for the history dependent response which is reflected in hysteresis, stress relaxation and creep behavior. The relative insensitivity of the hysteresis loss to strain rate suggests that a continuous spectrum, $S(\tau)$, may be used to establish the following generalized reduced relaxation function $G(t)$:

$$G(t) = [1 + \int_0^\infty S(\tau) \exp(-t/\tau) d\tau] / [1 + \int_0^\infty S(\tau) d\tau] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } S(\tau) = \frac{C}{\tau} \text{ for } \tau_1 < \tau < \tau_2 \quad (5)$$

$$= 0 \text{ elsewhere}$$

Where C is a constant. The reduced relaxation function $G(t)$ can be determined experimentally by normalization of the stress relaxation data with the initial load as shown below:

$$G(t) = \frac{T(t)}{T(0)} \quad (6)$$

Where $T(t)$ is the stress (or load) at any time and $T(0)$ is the initial stress (or load) for a stress relaxation experiment. The relaxation spectrum $S(\tau)$ given in Eq. (5) has been used to represent the history dependent behavior of a wide variety of materials conveniently in terms of the three parameters C , τ_1 , and τ_2 . High value of C indicates rapid relaxation of stress. τ_1 and τ_2 outline the time interval where stress relaxation is the most active. Table 3 shows the relaxation spectra of the high modulus fibers comparing with the relaxation spectra of the other fibers which have been characterized in our laboratory. These fibers represent a reasonable range of strength, elasticity, viscosity and strain for all the textile fibers in use at this time. An examination of the values of C for these fibers indicates that C associates with the intrinsic mechanical properties of fibers quite well. The C values within the range .004 to .025 indicate a stiff and strong fiber, while C values beyond .12 represent fibers that flow easily. It is interesting to note

Table 3. Relaxation Spectra for Various Fibers

$$s = C/\tau, \tau_1 < \tau < \tau_2$$

Fiber	C	1	2
Fiberglass ECC*	.0043	2.9100	550000
PRD 49 (predecessor of Kevlar 49)	.0097	28.6900	38000
Graphite T-300*	.0181	9.1641	160000
Kevlar 49*	.0256	1.5904	360000
Spider Silk	.0260	.0643	300000
Polyester HT	.0366	.1004	480000
Polyester MT	.0378	.0252	5400
Nylon 6 MT	.0430	.0962	60000
Nylon 6 UD	.1200	.1293	45000
Hard Elastic Polypropylene	.1638	2.0609	890000

*Fibers characterized in this study.

HT = high tenacity; MT = medium tenacity; UD = undrawn

that PRD 49 (the predecessor of the Kevlar 49 fibers), which lacks the level of toughness of Kevlar 49, has a lower C value. In general, τ_1 for the high modulus fibers should be expected to be greater than one second.

With the relaxation spectra, we can obtain the predicted values of the reduced relaxation function. As shown in Figs. 9a to 9c, the agreement between the computed and experimental reduced relaxation function is quite good for the high modulus fibers. The vertical bars in these figures show the dispersion of experimental stress relaxation data which is related to the strain level and the nonuniformity of the specimens. The relaxation spectra can also be used to predict other visco-elastic properties. For example, the damping characteristics of the high modulus fibers predicted in Fig. 10 show qualitative agreement with our experimental observations, i.e. the hysteresis loss of these fibers is relatively insensitive to strain rate over a few decades at low strain rates and that Kevlar fibers are tougher than graphite and fiberglass.

Figure 9. Experimental and Theoretical Reduced Stress Relaxation Functions of High Modulus Fibers

Figure 10. Prediction of the Frequency Response of High Modulus Fibers

CONCLUSIONS

Experimental observations show that high modulus fibers such as fiberglass, Kevlar and graphite are no exception to the rule that polymeric materials have non-linear stress-strain relationship which depend on strain history. The hysteresis loss for these fibers are not proportional to strain rate. Fractional stress relaxations are approximately linear functions of the logarithm of time. The rate of stress relaxation is the lowest for fiberglass even though its apparent modulus is lower than that of Kevlar and graphite fibers. The stress on Kevlar 49 fibers relaxes faster than fiberglass and graphite fibers under strain.

It has been demonstrated that a quasilinear viscoelastic model can be used to represent the stress-strain-time behavior of the high modulus fibers in terms of a continuous relaxation spectrum. This model can be used to form one dimensional constitutive equations for the high modulus fibers when sufficient information on the creep and dynamic mechanical properties of these fibers are available. Consequently, the quasilinear viscoelastic model provides a basis for the incorporation of the material properties of the high modulus fibers in the mechanistic analysis of fibrous assemblies and composite structures.

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